

Effect of different Anions on Phosphate Adsorption by Soils

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The effect of different anions on phosphate adsorption by ten surface soils representing important benchmark soil series of Punjab has been investigated. Phosphate adsorption increases with increase in equilibrium concentration. The adsorption isotherms are L-shaped for most of the soils. Highest amount of phosphate is adsorbed in the presence of CO_3^{2-} ions. Presence of HCO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} ions reduce phosphate adsorption whereas NO_3^- ions do not compete with phosphate for adsorption sites. The phosphate adsorption is inversely related with pH. The adsorption data conform to the Freundlich and Langmuir equations.

After nitrogen, phosphorus is the second most important nutrient element which limits agricultural production. Most of the soils in India are deficient in phosphorus. To ameliorate its deficiency the farmers have to use phosphatic fertilisers. When these fertilisers are applied to soils, the phosphate ions are adsorbed onto the surface of soil colloids with consequent reduction in their mobility and availability to crops. The salt-affected soils especially contain high concentrations of CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and Cl^- ions. Being negatively charged, these anions are likely to modify the adsorption and fixation of applied phosphates in soils. However, the extent to which the anions affect phosphate adsorption and the mechanism responsible for modification of phosphate adsorption behaviour of soils in the presence of different anions are not known.

Several workers¹ have studied the effect of different anions on phosphate adsorption using pure minerals. Their findings can not be extrapolated to natural systems because such monomineralic systems are rarely found in nature and most soils contain various minerals of different particle sizes. The present investigation was undertaken to evaluate the effect of different anions commonly found in soils on phosphate adsorption by widely occurring and agriculturally important soils of the region.

Results and Discussion

Phosphorus adsorption by soils: The amount of phosphate adsorbed by soils is plotted against the equilibrium concentration in Fig. 1. It is evident that P adsorption increased with increase in equilibrium concentration. However, the amount of phosphate adsorbed at a particular equilibrium concentration was different for different soils. The adsorption isotherms were L-shaped for all soils except Jassi Pauwali for which these were S-shaped.

Of the arid region soils, Gahri Bhagi adsorbed highest amounts of phosphate in the presence of CO_3^{2-} ions and the lowest amount in the presence of HCO_3^- ions. Jodhpur Ramana soil adsorbed highest amounts of phosphate in the presence of CO_3^{2-} , Cl^- and NO_3^- ions. In the semi-arid region soils, the highest amount of phosphate was adsorbed

Fig. 1 Effect of various anions on phosphate adsorption by Nabha soil at 25°.

by Nabha soil in the presence of CO_3^{2-} , Cl^- and NO_3^- ions. In the humid region soils, Dhar soil had greater adsorption capacity for phosphate absorption as compared to Chamror soil.

Effect of different anions on phosphate adsorption by soils: The effect of different anions on phosphate adsorption by Gahri Bhagi, Fatehpur, Kanjli and Nabha soils was found to follow the sequence: $\text{CO}_3^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^-$. Lodhawal, Chamror and Jassi Pauwali soils showed almost similar phosphate adsorption behaviour in the presence of different anions, following the sequence: $\text{CO}_3^{2-} > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{HCO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$. The effect of various anions on phosphate adsorption by Jodhpur Ramana soil was in the order: $\text{NO}_3^- > \text{CO}_3^{2-} > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^-$. In Dhar and Sadhu soils, the effect of various anions on phosphate adsorption was variable at lower and higher concentrations of phosphate.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF SOIL SAMPLES

Soil	Sand %	Silt %	Clay %	pH	EC dS/m	OC %	CaCO ₃ %	CEC (Cmol/kg)
Gahri Bhagi	53.6	27.8	18.6	7.9	0.25	0.22	0.6	7.8
Jassi Pauwali	80.9	14.1	5.0	8.2	0.19	0.09	2.2	6.1
Jodhpur Ramana	72.5	18.5	9.0	8.1	0.18	0.09	3.0	5.6
Fatehpur	92.4	4.1	3.5	7.8	0.21	0.12	0.1	2.8
Kanjli	44.5	37.3	18.4	3.5	0.24	0.40	1.0	10.1
Nabha	38.9	42.7	19.0	8.0	0.18	0.43	0.2	11.1
Lodhowal	19.4	63.6	17.0	8.2	0.21	0.54	1.9	13.4
Sadhu	5.4	34.9	59.7	8.2	0.27	0.71	0.8	30.4
Chamror	42.0	43.4	14.6	7.0	0.20	0.91	—	11.7
Dhar	34.6	48.6	16.8	7.6	0.30	0.56	0.4	10.8

A perusal of the data on phosphate adsorption in the presence of various anions indicated that the selectivity of soil adsorption surfaces for phosphate was higher in the presence of CO₃²⁻ and NO₃⁻ anions and lower in the presence of HCO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ anions; the effect of Cl⁻ was intermediate. Presence of CO₃²⁻ and NO₃⁻ increased the selectivity coefficients of soils for phosphate adsorption whereas HCO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ decreased it. Phosphate adsorption in the presence of various anions indicated that in the presence of CO₃²⁻ ions, all the soils except Jodhpur Ramana adsorbed highest amount of phosphate. This may be attributed to the content of CaCO₃ in these soils. Since Jodhpur Ramana soil had the highest amount of calcium carbonate (Table 1), the effect of addition of CO₃²⁻ in the supporting electrolyte may have been mitigated by the dissolution of native calcite in this soil in other electrolyte solutions to release CO₃²⁻ ions. Singh and Dass² reported that phosphate fixation in soils varied with the nature of the soil and amount of CaCO₃ present.

In view of the fact that all soil samples carry net negative charge in the pH range of experimental conditions and the phosphate concentration is relatively low as compared to that of the anions in the supporting electrolytes, it is obvious that the P was specifically adsorbed by these soils³, i.e. the phosphate adsorption was not due to simple electrostatic attraction of positively charged sites on soil adsorption complex for negatively charged phosphate anions in solution. As highest amount of phosphate was adsorbed in the presence of CO₃²⁻ anions followed by NO₃⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻ and HCO₃⁻ anions, it appears that CO₃²⁻ and NO₃⁻ ions may not be competing for adsorption on same sites where phosphate ions are adsorbed. Another reason for higher adsorption in the presence of CO₃²⁻ ions may be precipitation of complex phosphate carbonates (such as carbonate apatite) mediated by CO₃²⁻ ions. On the other hand, HCO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ ions may be competing with phosphate ions for adsorption on the same sites thereby reducing phosphate adsorption.

Relationship between pH and phosphate adsorption : The equilibrium pH of different soils in the presence of various anions is given in Table 2. The phosphate adsorption decreased with increase in pH. The mean value of equilibrium pH in the presence of various anions was in the order : CO₃²⁻ > HCO₃⁻ > Cl⁻ ≈ SO₄²⁻ > NO₃⁻. Although the mean value of equilibrium pH in the presence of CO₃²⁻ ions was highest, relatively higher amount of phosphate was retained by all soils probably due to precipitation of phosphates as discussed earlier. The effect of other anions can be interpreted on the basis of equilibrium pH. Excluding CO₃²⁻ ions, in most of the soils, phosphate adsorption was highest in the presence of NO₃⁻ ions and lowest in the presence of HCO₃⁻ ions, being intermediate in the presence of Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ ions. There is an inverse relationship between pH and phosphate adsorption. This may be due to the fact that as pH increased, the activity of OH⁻ also increased. The increased OH⁻ ion activity may have depressed phosphate adsorption by competing for the same sites on which phosphate ions are adsorbed by soils. Higher phosphate adsorption in the presence of NO₃⁻ ions appeared to be due to relatively limited competition from OH⁻ ions at low pH of NO₃⁻ system (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ANIONS ON pH OF EQUILIBRIUM SOLUTIONS

Soil	pH				
	CO ₃ ²⁻	HCO ₃ ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	Cl ⁻	NO ₃ ⁻
Gahri Bhagi	11.24	9.07	8.36	8.27	8.08
Jassi Pauwali	11.37	9.19	8.8	8.10	8.01
Jodhpur Ramana	10.76	9.12	9.0	8.29	7.96
Fatehpur	10.02	9.23	7.17	7.47	7.36
Kanjli	10.15	9.17	7.65	8.20	6.98
Lodhowal	9.89	9.01	8.16	8.15	8.17
Nabha	11.23	9.20	7.67	7.72	7.48
Sadhu	11.33	9.35	8.20	8.10	8.09
Chamror	11.32	9.07	7.29	7.64	7.68
Dhar	10.07	8.76	6.72	7.24	6.98
Mean	10.74	9.12	7.90	7.92	7.68

Application of adsorption equations : The phosphate adsorption data conformed to empirical Freundlich adsorption equation,

$$\log x/m = \log K + 1/n \log C$$

where, x is the amount of phosphate adsorbed by the soil, C the equilibrium concentration, K and n are constants. Plots of $\log x/m$ versus $\log C$ were linear indicating that the data conformed to Freundlich equation. The values of K which indicate the strength of adsorption are given in Table 3. These data suggest that phosphate was adsorbed more strongly by Nabha soil and relatively weakly by Jassi Pauwali soil as compared to other soils. Phosphate was adsorbed most strongly in the presence of CO_3^{2-} ions and least strongly in the presence of HCO_3^- ions as indicated by the highest and lowest value of K for Kanjli, Nabha, Fatehpur and Gahri Bhagi soils. In Lodhowal, Sadhu, Jodhpur Ramana, Jassi Pauwali and Dhar soils, phosphate was adsorbed more strongly in the presence of NO_3^- ions.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ANIONS ON FREUNDLICH CONSTANTS FOR PHOSPHATE ADSORPTION

Soil	Anion	K	n
Gahri Bhagi	CO_3^{2-}	0.871	0.944
	NO_3^-	0.331	0.727
	SO_4^{2-}	0.331	0.833
	Cl^-	0.245	0.857
	HCO_3^-	0.126	0.680
Jassi Pauwali	CO_3^{2-}	0.309	0.778
	NO_3^-	0.309	0.778
	SO_4^{2-}	0.126	0.833
	Cl^-	0.302	1.00
	HCO_3^-	0.182	0.714
Jodhpur Ramana	CO_3^{2-}	0.794	1.37
	NO_3^-	0.922	1.24
	SO_4^{2-}	0.457	1.00
	Cl^-	0.575	1.19
	HCO_3^-	0.426	1.15
Fatehpur	CO_3^{2-}	2.951	2.30
	NO_3^-	0.977	1.62
	SO_4^{2-}	0.645	1.18
	Cl^-	0.426	1.12
	HCO_3^-	0.316	1.0
Kanjli	CO_3^{2-}	0.870	0.941
	NO_3^-	0.692	1.09
	SO_4^{2-}	0.282	0.9
	Cl^-	0.282	0.9
	HCO_3^-	0.121	0.714
Lodhowal	CO_3^{2-}	0.549	0.75
	NO_3^-	1.29	1.50
	SO_4^{2-}	0.716	1.38
	Cl^-	0.716	1.33
	HCO_3^-	0.422	0.92
Nabha	CO_3^{2-}	2.14	1.50
	NO_3^-	1.74	1.45

Table-3 (Contd.)

Sadhu	SO_4^{2-}	1.05	1.28
	Cl^-	1.74	2.00
	HCO_3^-	0.525	1.00
	CO_3^{2-}	0.676	1.0
	NO_3^-	1.91	3.02
Chamror	SO_4^{2-}	0.562	1.0
	Cl^-	1.20	1.78
	HCO_3^-	0.513	1.20
	CO_3^{2-}	0.944	1.40
	NO_3^-	0.407	0.944
Dhar	SO_4^{2-}	0.363	1.00
	Cl^-	0.112	1.30
	HCO_3^-	0.363	1.00
	CO_3^{2-}	0.724	0.928
	NO_3^-	1.45	2.0
	SO_4^{2-}	0.933	1.57
	Cl^-	1.45	2.15
	HCO_3^-	0.933	1.25

The data were also fitted to the Langmuir equation,

$$c/x = 1/bk + c/b$$

where, c is the equilibrium concentration of solution, x the amount of phosphate adsorbed per unit weight of the soil, b the constant known as adsorption maxima and K is another constant which is a measure of the binding energy. A linear relationship was obtained on plotting c/x vs c , indicating that phosphate adsorption data conformed to Langmuir equation.

The adsorption maxima varied greatly from one soil to other (Table 4) in the presence of various anions as : Jassi Pauwali > Gahri Bhagi > Lodhowal > Chamror > Nabha > Kanjli > Fatehpur > Dhar > Jodhpur Ramana > Sadhu. The adsorption maxima was not related to any single characteristic of these soils but depended mainly on clay, calcium carbonate and organic matter contents and cation exchange capacity of soils. The effect of various anions on the adsorption maxima was in the sequence : $\text{Cl}^- > \text{CO}_3^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$. Different soils exhibited highest adsorption maxima in the presence of Cl^- ions and lowest values in the presence of SO_4^{2-} ions.

The binding energy constant K (Table 4) was also affected by the nature of anions in the following sequence : $\text{CO}_3^{2-} > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^-$. Obviously phosphate was adsorbed more tightly in the presence of CO_3^{2-} ions as indicated by higher binding energy constants (Table 4).

Evaluation of partial molar free energy change : The change in partial molar free energy of the system (\bar{G}) as a result of adsorption was evaluated as given by Bailey *et al.*⁴. From the averaged values of \bar{G} (Table 5) it is clear that in Gahri Bhagi, Fatehpur, Kanjli and Nabha soils, the highest values of \bar{G} were observed in the presence of CO_3^{2-} ions followed by NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cl^- and HCO_3^- ions,

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ANIONS ON LANGMUIR CONSTANTS (*b, K*) FOR PHOSPHATE ADSORPTION

Soil	Adsorption maxima ($\mu\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{g}$)						K					
	CO_3^{2-}	Cl^-	SO_4^{2-}	NO_3^-	HCO_3^-	Mean	CO_3^{2-}	Cl^-	SO_4^{2-}	NO_3^-	HCO_3^-	Mean
Gahri Bhagi	45.0	18.75	21.25	—	—	28.93	0.0007	0.0007	0.0008	—	—	0.0007
Jassi Pauwali	55.0	125.0	—	55.0	—	40.83	0.0002	0.0001	—	0.0009	—	0.0004
Jodhpur Ramana	10.0	9.17	8.75	15.0	8.33	10.25	0.0020	0.0020	0.0018	0.0019	0.0015	0.0014
Fatehpur	7.5	13.33	8.83	8.0	17.50	10.93	0.0120	0.0010	0.0025	0.0035	0.0006	0.0039
Kanjli	12.5	10.0	13.75	14.0	23.75	14.80	0.0030	0.0012	0.0011	0.0018	0.0003	0.0015
Lodhowal	25.0	20.0	16.67	18.75	55.0	27.08	0.0012	0.0009	0.0009	0.0016	0.0003	0.0010
Nabha	12.5	10.0	11.25	22.5	32.5	17.75	0.0061	0.0042	0.0029	0.0021	0.0005	0.0031
Sadhu	11.25	7.14	13.75	10.0	6.25	9.68	0.0025	0.0044	0.0016	0.0047	0.0025	0.0031
Chamror	25.0	—	18.75	26.67	18.75	22.29	0.0011	—	0.0007	0.0005	0.0007	0.0007
Dhar	13.33	6.25	12.50	10.83	11.25	10.83	0.0024	0.0073	0.0021	0.0037	0.0025	0.0036
Mean	21.71	24.40	13.89	20.08	21.67	—	0.0031	0.0024	0.0016	0.0023	0.0011	—

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ANIONS ON AVERAGED \bar{G} (PARTIAL MOLAR FREE ENERGY CHANGE) VALUES

Soil	\bar{G} (cal mol ⁻¹)				
	CO_3^{2-}	Cl^-	NO_3^-	HCO_3^-	SO_4^{2-}
Gahri Bhagi	287.02	120.77	176.17	101.68	151.63
Jassi Pauwali	161.71	91.24	206.14	118.92	78.02
Jodhpur Ramana	177.50	148.28	207.13	109.03	132.90
Fatehpur	450.55	120.78	160.90	104.65	160.88
Kanjli	279.31	108.39	193.05	79.68	139.25
Lodhowal	267.74	170.75	239.42	166.01	151.67
Nabha	375.82	264.30	338.63	156.96	225.05
Sadhu	221.35	197.31	280.15	128.95	181.30
Chamror	225.59	169.90	148.37	142.23	129.59
Dhar	245.97	237.18	257.46	209.84	194.96

suggesting a greater driving force for phosphate adsorption in the presence of CO_3^{2-} ions compared with other anions. In Lodhowal, Chamror and Dhar soils, the driving force of phosphate adsorption was lowest in the presence of SO_4^{2-} ions. In Jodhpur Ramana and Sadhu soils, the averaged value of \bar{G} was highest in the presence of NO_3^- ions.

Experimental

Surface soil samples from ten benchmark soils of Punjab representing Gahri Bhagi, Jassi Pauwali, Jodhpur Ramana (from arid region), Fatehpur, Kanjli, Lodhowal, Nabha, Sadhu (from semi-arid region), Chamror and Dhar (from humid region) soil series were used. These soil samples after drying in air, were crushed and passed through 300 mesh sieve. The samples were then stored in sealed glass containers.

The mineralogical analyses of sand, silt and clay fractions by X-ray diffraction technique indicated that sand and silt fractions of these soils contained quartz, micas and feldspars with minor amounts of ferromagnesian silicates such as biotite, hornblende, chlorite and zircon. Calcite was the only carbonate present in these soils. Illite was the predominant clay mineral in the clay fractions of Gahri Bhagi, Jassi Pauwali, Jodhpur Ramana, Fatehpur, Nabha, Chamror and Dhar soils followed by smectite, whereas smectite was predominant in Lodhowal and Sadhu soils.

All the soils contained 10–15% kaolinite and minor amounts of vermiculite and/or chlorite. Although the surface area measurements were not carried out, on the basis of particle size distribution data (Table 1), it can be concluded that Sadhu soils had highest surface area. The surface area of Gahri Bhagi, Kanjli, Nabha, Lodhowal, Dhar and Chamror soils was found intermediate and that of Jassi Pauwali, Jodhpur Ramana and Fatehpur soils being low.

The soil sample (1 g) was taken in each of the nine reagent bottles (125 ml). Stock solution (0, 3, 4...10 ml) of phosphorus (50 ppm) was added in different reagent bottles and mixed thoroughly. An electrolyte solution (0.02 M of NaCl, NaNO_3 , NaHCO_3 , Na_2CO_3 or Na_2SO_4) was then added in each bottle and the final volume was made to 50 ml by adding distilled water so that the resultant concentration of electrolyte in each solution was 0.01 M. The bottles were incubated at 25° with frequent shaking for 48 h. The soil suspensions were then centrifuged and the amount of phosphorus in the extract was determined spectrophotometrically by ascorbic method⁵.

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